

Knowledge co-production in the Urban Living Labs

Recommendations for policy

- Through an ULL approach with particular collaboration between researchers and public administrations, knowledge is contextualised and shapes project details to ensure local relevance.
- Participating in knowledge co-production provides public administrations with a mechanism for raising awareness of NbS within the organisation and on a political level.
- In order for the produced knowledge to have an impact in the organisation communication targeting the practice is essential. This needs to be tailored for the stakeholders with regards to communication style, language and medium.

This brief provides information about the outcome of REGREEN research on the process of knowledge co-production that took place in the European Urban Living Labs.

Urban Living Labs (ULLs) are lifted forward as an approach that explores in real-time society-science interfaces and function as arenas for learning as they allow to test novel processes, actor constellations and practices that otherwise may not unfold. A common element for these projects are that they apply transdisciplinary approaches, in which knowledge co-production takes place across disciplines and sectors, integrating more than academic expertise and highlighting practice-based knowledge. Research methods are often of explorative and experimental character and aim at long-term strategies and solutions. Learning and reflexivity are core objectives and qualities of an ULL to detect mechanisms that are scalable and transferable.

Urban Living Labs within REGREEN

Central to the REGREEN project was the use of Urban Living Labs (ULLs), three in Europe (Aarhus, Paris Region and Velika Gorica) and three in China (Beijing, Ningbo and Shanghai). The Chinese ULLs differed from the European ULLs due to its lack of direct involvement of public administrations. The European ULLs were represented by two municipality organisations (Aarhus Municipality and Velika Gorica Municipality) and one regional think tank (Paris Region). Within the project the ULLs had a central role as an arena for co-creation of knowledge involving local citizens, schools, businesses, organisations and public administrations. Within the ULLs different approaches, methods and tools were developed and applied that could be integrated into decision support systems, guidelines and standards for developing and deploying urban NbS at a systemic and strategic level.

A training workshop for technicians has been run by IPR at all three European ULLs
 © Marc Barra

Approach

In order to analyse the knowledge co-production taken place within the REGREEN project we carried out document analysis to explore the involvement of the three European ULLs within the different tasks. We also carried out semi-structured interviews with the local contact persons for all three ULLs to understand the role of the public administrations within the knowledge co-production process and how the project has influenced their respective organisation.

Training session, Vesterbro Torv, Aarhus © Signe M. Iversen

Do you know that...

... for Aarhus municipality REGREEN has provided an opportunity to increase the political awareness of NbS but also to increase the general awareness of NbS within the organisation.

... in Velika Gorica the knowledge produced within REGREEN has been put into action through the comprehensive plan and the three programs (Clean air, Climate change and Environmental protection).

... in Paris Region the depavement strategy developed within REGREEN has moved into planning and policies on a municipal level.

Knowledge co-production within the European ULLs

The key outcomes of the study are summarised as follows:

- Public administrations took on different roles with regards to knowledge co-production for the different tasks. This ranged from providing local data sets, contextualised task, towards driving activities that could directly feed into policy and planning documents.
- An important component of the knowledge co-production from the perspective of the public administrations was the peer-to-peer knowledge exchange. This was facilitated through organised meetings between the ULL contact persons, field visits during the project meetings on site as well as the training workshop developed and run by the Paris Region ULL.
- All three European ULL recognised the importance of REGREEN for raising political and broader awareness of NbS within their respective organisations. This was facilitated through the contact persons for each ULL engagement and communication with a wider set of stakeholders possible through the ULL. Important here was also the project meeting on site in each ULL which allowed members of staff from the organisation to partake and meet the members of the consortium.
- The public administrations benefited in different ways depending on the status of on-going work with NbS. For Paris region and Aarhus municipality the new knowledge provided by REGREEN has at large fed into on-going work and policies. In the municipality of Velika Gorica the knowledge produced have allowed new policies and programs to be developed in support of NbS.

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